

FLORENTIN SMARANDACHE
**A Function in the Number
Theory**

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A FUNCTION IN THE NUMBER THEORY

Summary

In this paper I shall construct a function η having the following properties:

$$\forall \eta \in Z \quad n \neq 0 \quad (\eta(n))! = M \cdot n, \quad (1)$$

$$\eta(n) \text{ is the smallest natural number with the property (1).} \quad (2)$$

We consider: $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ and $N^* = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Lemma 1. $\forall k, p \in N^*, p \neq 1, k$ is uniquely written under the shape: $k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$ where $a_{n_i}^{(p)} = \frac{p^{n_i-1}}{p-1}$, $i = \overline{1, l}$, $n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l > 0$ and $1 \leq t_j \leq p-1$, $j = \overline{1, l-1}$, $1 \leq t_l \leq p$, $n_j, t_j \in N$, $i = \overline{1, l}$ $l \in N^*$.

Proof. The string $(a_n^{(p)})_{n \in N^*}$ consists of strictly increasing infinite natural numbers and $a_{n+1}^{(p)} - 1 = p \cdot a_n^{(p)}$, $\forall n \in N^*, p$ is fixed,

$$a_1^{(p)} = 1, a_2^{(p)} = 1 + p, a_3^{(p)} = 1 + p + p^2, \dots \Rightarrow N^* = \bigcup_{n \in N^*} ((a_n^{(p)}, a_{n+1}^{(p)}) \cap N^*)$$

where $(a_n^{(p)}, a_{n+1}^{(p)}) \cap (a_{n+1}^{(p)}, a_{n+2}^{(p)}) = \emptyset$ because $a_n^{(p)} < a_{n+1}^{(p)} < a_{n+2}^{(p)}$.

Let $k \in N^*$, $N^* = \bigcup_{n \in N^*} ((a_n^{(p)}, a_{n+1}^{(p)}) \cap N^*) \Rightarrow \exists! n_1 \in N^* : k \in (a_{n_1}^{(p)}, a_{n_1+1}^{(p)}) \Rightarrow k$ is uniquely written under the shape $k = \left[\frac{k}{a_{n_1}^{(p)}} \right] a_{n_1}^{(p)} + r_1$ (integer division theorem). We note $k = \left[\frac{k}{a_{n_1}^{(p)}} \right] = t_1 \Rightarrow k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + r_1$, $r_1 < a_{n_1}^{(p)}$.

If $r_1 = 0$, as $a_{n_1}^{(p)} \leq k \leq a_{n_1+1}^{(p)} - 1 \Rightarrow 1 \leq t_1 \leq p$ and Lemma 1 is proved.

If $r_1 \neq 0 \Rightarrow \exists! n_2 \in N^* : r_1 \in (a_{n_2}^{(p)}, a_{n_2+1}^{(p)})$; $a_{n_1}^{(p)} > r_1 > n_1 > n_2$, $r_1 \neq 0$ and $a_{n_1}^{(p)} \leq k \leq a_{n_1+1}^{(p)} - 1 \Rightarrow 1 \leq t_1 \leq p-1$ because we have $t_1 \leq (a_{n_1+1}^{(p)} - 1 - r_1) : a_{n_1}^{(p)} < p_1$.

The procedure continues similarly. After a finite number of steps l , we achieve $r_l = 0$, as $k = \text{finite}$, $k \in N^*$ and $k > r_1 > r_2 > \dots > r_l = 0$ and between 0 and k there is only a finite number of distinct natural numbers.

Thus:

k is uniquely written: $k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + r_1$, $1 \leq t_1 \leq p-1$, r is uniquely written: $r_1 = t_2 a_{n_2}^{(p)} + r_2$, $n_2 < n_1$,

$$1 \leq t_2 \leq p-1,$$

r_{l-1} is uniquely written: $r_{l-1} = t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)} + r_l$ and $r_l = 0$,

$$n_l < n_{l-1}, 1 \leq l \leq p,$$

$\Rightarrow k$ is uniquely written under the shape $k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$ with $n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l; n_l > 0$ because $n_l \in N^*$, $1 \leq t_j \leq p-1$, $j = \overline{1, l-1}$, $1 \leq t_l \leq p$, $l \geq 1$.

Let $k \in N^*$, $k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$, with $a_{n_i}^{(p)} = \frac{p^{n_i} - 1}{p - 1}$, $i = \overline{1, l}$, $l \geq 1$, $n_i, t_i \in N^*$, $i = \overline{1, l}$, $n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l > 0$, $1 \leq t_j \leq p-1$, $j = \overline{1, l-1}$, $1 \leq t_l \leq p$.

I construct the function η_p , $p = \text{prime} > 0$, $\eta_p : N^* \rightarrow N^*$ thus:

$$\forall n \in N^* \quad \eta_p(a_n^{(p)}) = p^n,$$

$$\eta_p(t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}) = t_1 \eta_p(a_{n_1}^{(p)}) + \dots + t_l \eta_p(a_{n_l}^{(p)}).$$

Note 1. The function η_p is well defined for each natural number.

Proof.

Lemma 2. $\forall k \in N^* \Rightarrow k$ is uniquely written as $k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$ with the conditions from Lemma 1 $\Rightarrow \exists! t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} = \eta_p(t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)})$ and $t_1^{n_1} + t_l^{n_l} \in N^*$.

Lemma 3. $\forall k \in N^*$, $\forall p \in N$, $p = \text{prime} \Rightarrow k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$ with the conditions from Lemma 2 $\Rightarrow \eta_p(k) = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}$.

It is known that $\left[\frac{a_1 + \dots + a_n}{b} \right] \geq \left[\frac{a_1}{b} \right] + \dots + \left[\frac{a_n}{b} \right]$ $\forall a_i, b \in N^*$ where through $[\alpha]$ we have written the integer side of number α . I shall prove that p 's powers sum from the natural numbers make up the result factors $(t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l})!$ is $\geq k$;

$$\left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}}{p} \right] \geq \left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1}}{p} \right] + \dots + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l}}{p} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1-1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l-1}$$

$\vdots$

$$\left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}}{p^{n_l}} \right] \geq \left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1}}{p^{n_l}} \right] + \dots + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l}}{p^{n_l}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1-n_l} + \dots + t_l p^0$$

$\vdots$

$$\left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}}{p^{n_1}} \right] \geq \left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1}}{p^{n_1}} \right] + \dots + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l}}{p^{n_1}} \right] = t_1 p^0 + \dots + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l}}{p^{n_1}} \right].$$

Adding $\Rightarrow p$'s powers sum is $\geq t_1 (p^{n_1-1} + \dots + p^0) + \dots + t_l (p^{n_l-1} + \dots + p^0) = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)} =$

k .

Theorem 1. *The function n_p , $p = \text{prime}$, defined previously, has the following properties:*

- (1) $\forall k \in N^*$, $(n_p(k))! = Mp^k$.
- (2) $\eta_p(k)$ is the smallest number with the property (1).

Proof.

(1) results from Lemma 3.

(2) $\forall k \in N^*$, $p \geq 2 \Rightarrow k = t_1 a_{n_1}^{(p)} + \dots + t_l a_{n_l}^{(p)}$ (by Lemma 2) is uniquely written, where:

$$n_i, t_i \in N^*, n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l > 0, a_{n_i}^{(p)} = \frac{p^{n_i} - 1}{p - 1} \in N^*, i = \overline{1, l}, 1 \leq t_j \leq p - 1, j = \overline{1, l - 1}, 1 < t_l < p.$$

$$\Rightarrow \eta_p(k) = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}. \text{ I note: } z = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l}.$$

Let us prove the z is the smallest natural number with the property (1). I suppose by the method of reduction ad absurdum that $\exists \gamma \in N$, $\gamma < z$:

$$\gamma! = Mp^k;$$

$$\gamma < z \Rightarrow \gamma \leq z - 1 \Rightarrow (z - 1)! = Mp^k.$$

$$z - 1 = t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1; n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_l \geq 0 \text{ and } n_j \in N, j = \overline{1, l};$$

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - 1} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^{n_{l-1} - 1} + t_l p^{n_l - 1} - 1 \text{ as } \left[\frac{-1}{p} \right] = -1 \text{ because } p \geq 2,$$

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p^{n_l}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - n_l} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^{n_{l-1} - n_l} + t_l p^0 - 1 \text{ as } \left[\frac{-1}{p^{n_l}} \right] = -1 \text{ as } p \geq 2, n_l \geq 1,$$

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p^{n_{l-1} + 1}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - n_{l-1} - 1} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^{n_{l-1} - n_{l-1} - 1} + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l} - 1}{p^{n_{l-1} + 1}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - n_{l-1} - 1} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^{n_{l-1} - n_{l-1} - 1}$$

because $0 < t_l p^{n_l} - 1 \leq p \cdot p^{n_l} - 1 < p^{n_l + 1}$ as $t_l < p$;

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p^{n_{l-1}}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - n_{l-1}} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^0 + \left[\frac{t_l p^{n_l} - 1}{p^{n_{l-1}}} \right] = t_1 p^{n_1 - n_{l-1}} + \dots + t_{l-1} p^0 \text{ as } n_{l-1} > n_l,$$

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p^{n_1}} \right] = t_1 p^0 + \left[\frac{t_2 p^{n_2} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1}{p^{n_1}} \right] = t_1 p^0.$$

$$\text{Because } 0 < t_2 p^{n_2} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1 \leq (p - 1)p^{n_2} + \dots + (p - 1)p^{n_l} + p \cdot p^{n_l} - 1 \leq (p - 1) \times \sum_{i=n_2}^{n_l} p^i + p^{n_l + 1} - 1 \leq (p - 1) \frac{p^{n_2 + 1}}{p - 1} = p^{n_2 + 1} - 1 < p^{n_1} - 1 < p^{n_1} \Rightarrow \left[\frac{t_2 p^{n_2} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1}{p^{n_1}} \right] = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{z - 1}{p^{n_1 + 1}} \right] = \left[\frac{t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1}{p^{n_1 + 1}} \right] = 0$$

because: $0 < t_1 p^{n_1} + \dots + t_l p^{n_l} - 1 < p^{n_1+1} - 1 < p^{n_1+1}$ according to a reasoning similar to the previous one.

Adding $\Rightarrow p$'s powers sum in the natural numbers which make up the product factors $(z-1)!$ is:

$t_1(p^{n_1-1} + \dots + p^0) + \dots + t_{l-1}(p^{n_{l-1}-1} + \dots + p^0) + t_l(p^{n_l-1} + \dots + p^0) - 1 \cdot n_l = k - n_l < k-1 < k$ because $n_l > 1 \Rightarrow (z-1)! \neq Mp^k$, this contradicts the supposition made.

$\Rightarrow \eta_p(k)$ is the smallest natural number with the property $(\eta_p(k))! = Mp^k$.

I construct a new function $\eta : Z \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow N$ as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \eta(\pm 1) = 0, \\ \forall n = \epsilon p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \text{ with } \epsilon = \pm 1, p_i = \text{prime}, \\ p_i \neq p_j \text{ for } i \neq j, \alpha_i \geq 1, i = \overline{1, s}, \eta(n) = \max_{i=\overline{1, s}} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\}. \end{cases}$$

Note 2. η is well defined and defined overall.

Proof.

(a) $\forall n \in Z, n \neq 0, n \neq \pm 1, n$ is uniquely written, independent of the order of the factors, under the shape of $n = \epsilon p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ with $\epsilon = \pm 1$ where $p_i = \text{prime}, p_i \neq p_j, \alpha_i \geq 1$ (decompose into prime factors in $Z = \text{factorial ring}$).

$\Rightarrow \exists! \eta(n) = \max_{i=\overline{1, s}} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\}$ as $s = \text{finite}$ and $\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i) \in N^*$ and $\exists \max_{i=\overline{1, s}} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\}$

(b) $n = \pm 1 \Rightarrow \exists! \eta(n) = 0$.

Theorem 2. *The function η previously defined has the following properties:*

- (1) $(\eta(n))! = Mn, \forall n \in Z \setminus \{0\}$;
- (2) $\eta(n)$ is the smallest natural number with this property.

Proof.

(a) $\eta(n) = \max_{i=\overline{1, s}} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\}, n = \epsilon \cdot p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}, (n \neq \pm 1); (\eta_{p_1}(\alpha_1))! = Mp_1^{\alpha_1}, \dots, (n_{p_s}(\alpha_s))! = Mp_s^{\alpha_s}$.

Supposing $\max_{i=\overline{1, s}} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\} = \eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}) \Rightarrow (\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}))! = Mp_{i_0}^{\alpha_{i_0}}, \eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}) \in N^*$ and because $(p_i, p_j) = 1, i \neq j,$

$\Rightarrow (\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}))! = Mp_j^{\alpha_j}, j = \overline{1, s}.$

$\Rightarrow (\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}))! = Mp_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}.$

(b) $n = \pm 1 \Rightarrow \eta(n) = 0; 0! = 1, 1 = M\epsilon \cdot 1 = Mn.$

$$(2) (a) n \neq \pm 1 \Rightarrow n = \epsilon p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \Rightarrow \eta(n) = \max_{i=1,s} \eta_{p_i}$$

$$\text{Let } \eta = \max_{i=1,s} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\} = \eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}), \quad 1 \leq i \leq s;$$

$\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0})$ is the smallest natural number with the property:

$$\begin{aligned} (\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}))! &= M p_{i_0}^{\alpha_{i_0}} \Rightarrow \forall \gamma \in N, \gamma < \eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}) \Rightarrow \gamma! \neq M p_{i_0}^{\alpha_{i_0}} \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow \gamma! \neq M \epsilon \cdot p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_{i_0}^{\alpha_{i_0}} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} = Mn. \end{aligned}$$

$\eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0})$ is the smallest natural number with the property.

(b) $n = \pm 1 \Rightarrow \eta(n) = 0$ and it is the smallest natural number $\Rightarrow 0$ is the smallest natural number with the property $0! = M(\pm 1)$.

Note 3. The functions η_p are increasing, not injective, on $N^* \rightarrow \{p^k | k = 1, 2, \dots\}$ they are surjective.

The function η is increasing, not injective, it is surjective on $Z \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow N \setminus \{1\}$.

CONSEQUENCE. Let $n \in N^*$, $n > 4$. Then $n = \text{prime} \Leftrightarrow \eta(n) = n$.

Proof.

$$" \Rightarrow " \quad n = \text{prime} \text{ and } n \geq 5 \Rightarrow \eta(n) = \eta_n(1) = n.$$

" $\Leftarrow$ " Let $\eta(n) = n$ and suppose by absurd that $n \neq \text{prime} \Rightarrow$

$$(a) \text{ or } n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s} \text{ with } s \geq 2, \alpha_i \in N^*, i = \overline{1, s},$$

$$\eta(n) = \max_{i=1,s} \{\eta_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\} = \eta_{p_{i_0}}(\alpha_{i_0}) < \alpha_{i_0} p_{i_0} < n$$

contradicts the assumption; or

$$(b) n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \text{ with } \alpha_1 \geq 2 \Rightarrow \eta(n) = \eta_{p_1}(\alpha_1) \leq p_1 \cdot \alpha_1 < p_1^{\alpha_1} = n$$

because $\alpha_1 \geq 2$ and $n > 4$ and it contradicts the hypothesis.

Application

1. Find the smallest natural number with the property: $n! = M(\pm 2^{31} \cdot 3^{27} \cdot 7^{13})$.

Solution

$$\eta(\pm 2^{31} \cdot 3^{27} \cdot 7^{13}) = \max\{\eta_2(31), \eta_3(27), \eta_7(13)\}.$$

Let us calculate $\eta_2(31)$; we make the string $(a_n^{(2)})_{n \in N^*} = 1, 3, 7, 15, 31, 63, \dots$

$$31 = 1 \cdot 31 \Rightarrow \eta_2(31) = \eta_2(1 \cdot 31) = 1 \cdot 2^5 = 32.$$

Let's calculate $\eta_3(27)$ making the string $(a_n^{(3)})_{n \in N^*} = 1, 4, 13, 40, \dots$; $27 = 2 \cdot 13 + 1 \Rightarrow \eta_3^{(27)} = \eta_3(2 \cdot 13 + 1 \cdot 1) = 2 \cdot \eta_3(13) + 1 \cdot \eta_3(1) = 2 \cdot 3^3 + 1 \cdot 3^1 = 54 + 3 = 57.$

Let's calculate $\eta_7(13)$; making the string $(a_n^{(7)})_{n \in N^*} = 1, 8, 57, \dots$; $13 = 1 \cdot 8 + 5 \cdot 1 \Rightarrow \eta_7(13) = 1 \cdot \eta_7(8) + 5 \cdot \eta_7(1) = 1 \cdot 7^2 + 5 \cdot 7^1 = 49 + 35 = 84 \Rightarrow \eta(\pm 2^{31} \cdot 3^{27} \cdot 7^{13}) = \max\{32, 57, 84\} = 84 \Rightarrow 84! = M(\pm 2^{31} \cdot 3^{27} \cdot 7^{13})$ and 84 is the smallest number with this property.

2. Which are the numbers with the factorial ending in 1000 zeros ?

Solution

$n = 10^{1000}$, $(\eta(n))! = M10^{1000}$ and it is the smallest number with this property.

$\eta(10^{1000}) = \eta(2^{1000} \cdot 5^{1000}) = \max\{\eta_2(1000), \eta_5(1000)\} = \eta_5(1 \cdot 781 + 1 \cdot 156 + 2 \cdot 31 + 1) = 1 \cdot 5^5 + 1 \cdot 5^4 + 2 \cdot 5^3 + 1 \cdot 5^2 = 4005$, 4005 is the smallest number with this property. 4006, 4007, 4008, 4009 verify the property but 4010 does not because $4010! = 4009!4010$ has 1001 zeros.

Florentin Smarandache

University of Craiova 17.11.1979

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